

OS-try
X
H-NMR

The University of Jordan
Faculty of Science
Department of Chemistry

Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
nmr500@ju.edu.jo

Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1931
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 11.55 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 12.22
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

OS-VAL
H-NMR

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Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
nmr500@ju.edu.jo

Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1911
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 11.14 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 ()
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 12.22
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

OS-VAL
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H-NMR

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Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1921
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 11.27 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 12.22
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

OS-PH
H-NMR

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Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1941
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 12.31 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 12.22
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

OS-PH-X

¹H NMR

10.5489	7.2579	6.6369	4.2156	4.2088	4.1631	4.1493	4.1354	4.1289	4.1223	4.1152	3.9908	3.9791	3.9199	3.8958	3.8617	3.8451	3.7890	3.7465	3.7284	3.7065	3.4971	3.4870	3.4772	3.4658	3.4446	3.4344	3.4251	3.4098	3.3993	3.3891	3.3832	3.3773	3.3620	3.0142	2.9998	2.9853	2.9709	2.4925	1.8705	1.8417	1.4215	1.4096	1.3950	1.2218	1.2158	1.2078	1.1987	1.1936	1.1482	1.1338	1.1193	0.8528	0.8361	0.8214	0.8067	0.7863	0.7716	0.7569
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16 15 14 13 12 11 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1 0 -1 ppm

1.00
0.10 1.20 0.53 5.00 0.34 1.64
48.80 21.14 2.97 17.28 2.86 5.48 7.55 32.11 11.91

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Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1951
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameter
Date_ 20230924
Time 13.00 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 (zg)
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 4
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 12.22
DW 50.000 us
DE 6.50 us
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 us
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

10.5854
8.3784
8.3611
6.6754
6.6172
6.5852
4.3953
4.2775
4.1452
4.1313
4.1172
4.1032
3.8706
3.8004
3.7767
3.7539
3.3869
3.3761
3.3652
3.3133
3.1825
2.8494
2.8245
2.4943
2.3815
1.9996
1.8560
1.6550
1.4389
1.4251
1.4106
1.3676
1.3546
1.3406
1.3265
1.1996
1.1855
1.1714
0.8482
0.8338

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Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassounch
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sept15jalal
EXPNO 1871
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 8.48 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 8.7
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

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Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1901
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 11.05 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 12.22
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00

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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1891
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 10.46 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zg
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 8
DS 2
SWH 10000.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.305176 Hz
AQ 3.2767999 sec
RG 22.83
DW 50.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 500.1335315 MHz
NUC1 1H
P1 12.00 usec
PLW1 14.30399990 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 131072
SF 500.1300091 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 0.40 Hz
GB 0
PC 5.00